

PHYSIOLOGICAL AND BIOCHEMICAL RESPONSE OF Bt COTTON IN RELATION TO SUCKING PEST UNDER UNPROTECTED CONDITION

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Abstract

The data recorded during kharif 2019 for various parameters in unprotected condition at Main Cotton Research Station, Navsari Agriculture University, Athwafarm, Surat-395007, Gujarat under AICRP on Cotton. Various parameters like Yield and yield attributes recorded at harvest. Jassid population (No/3 leaves) was significantly differed among BT genotypes under unprotected condition at 30, 60 and 90 DAS. Protein content was found in range of 2.25 to 8.75 mg/g of fresh leaf tissue under unprotected condition while phenol content was in range of 2.41 to 4.45 mg/g of fresh leaf. Highest phenol content was recorded in AJIT -199 BG-II and lower phenol content and higher reducing sugar was found in G. Cot. Hy-8 BG-II. Tannin content was found highest in ANKUR-3028 BG-II followed by AJIT-155BG-II while it was lowest in RHC-II BG-II. Flavanoid and Gossypol content were significantly differed among BT genotypes under unprotected condition. Highest Jassid population was found in RHC-II BG-II (2.80/3 leaves).

Key words: Jassid, Gossypol, Tannin**Introduction:**

Gossypium name of the genus is derived from the Arabic word goz, which refers to a soft substance. Cotton belongs to the genus *Gossypium* under tribe *Gossypieae* of family *Malvaceae* (Gledhill, 2008): *G. arboreum* and *G. herbaceum*, the old world cottons and *G. hirsutum* and *G. barbadense*, the new world cottons are commercially grown for their seed and fiber characteristics, (Naveen *et al.*, (1996). Many successful cotton cultivars have been developed from closely India is the pioneer country in the world for development of cotton hybrid for commercial cultivation (Anonymous, 2015). The major enemy of cotton production is sucking pest and insects. To find out the role of biochemical constituents in defense to sucking pest is major issue. In this connection,

the experiment was carried out to study the response of BT cotton to sucking pest under unprotected condition.

Materials and Methods:

The experiment was conducted during kharif 2019 for various parameters in unprotected condition in Random block design with three replication in field at Main Cotton Research Station, Navsari Agriculture University, Athwafarm, Surat-395007, Gujarat under AICRP on Cotton. Ten Bt cotton hybrids were selected for study. List of Bt cotton hybrids as below. Various parameters like Yield and yield attributes recorded at harvest. Biochemical and Jassid per three leaves data were collected at 30, 45 and 60 DAS (Days after sowing).

Sr. No.	Name of Bt	Sr. No.	Name of Bt
1	G. Cot. Hy.-8 BG-II	6	ANKUR- 3028 BG-II
2	G.Cot.Hy-10 BG-II	7	AJIT -155 BG-II
3	G.Cot.Hy-12 BG-II	8	AJIT -199 BG-II
4	GTHH-49 BG-II	9	BUNNY NCS-145
5	RHC-II BG-II	10	JAY BT

Jassid population: Jassid per three leaves data were collected at 30, 60 and 90 DAS and values shown in table were transformed values.

Protein content determination: Protein extraction and estimation elucidated by the method of Lowry *et al.*, (1951). Protein in the sample was estimated at 660 nm using bovine serum albumin as standard and expressed amount of protein mg per gm.

Phenol content determination: Phenol extraction and estimation elucidated by the method of Malick and Singh, (1980). Phenol in the sample was estimated at 650 nm using Catechol as standard and expressed amount of phenol mg per gm.

Reducing sugar determination: Reducing sugar extraction and estimation elucidated by the method of Somogyi (1952) and Miller (1959). Reducing sugar in the sample was estimated at 510 nm using D-Glucose as standard and expressed amount of reducing sugar mg per g.

Tannin determination: Tannin extraction and estimation elucidated by the method of Schanderl (1970). Tannin in the sample was estimated at 700 nm using Tannic acid as standard and expressed amount Tannin mg per 100g.

Flavanoid content determination: Flavanoid extraction and estimation were carried as per standard method of Thimmaiah (1999). Flavanoid content from samples were estimated at 500nm using standard curve of phloroglucinol and express amount of flavanoid as mg per g.

Gossypol content determination: Gossypol extraction and estimation elucidated by the method of Bell (1967). Gossypol in the sample was estimated at 550 nm using Gossypol acetate as standard and expressed amount of gossypol (%).

Results and Discussion:

Yield and Yield Attributes: The data recorded during kharif 2019 for various parameters in unprotected condition, were presented in Table 1. Plant height and no. of monopodia were significantly differed among BT genotypes under unprotected condition. No. of sympodia and Final plant population per net plot were non- significant among 10 BT genotypes under unprotected condition. No. of bolls per plant, Boll weight and seed cotton yield was significantly deviated due to genotypes under unprotected condition. Bolls per plant was observed significantly for GTHH-49 BG-II followed by AJIT -155 BG-II and G.Cot.Hy-12 BG-II under unprotected condition while boll weight was significantly higher for AJIT -199 BG-II followed by BUNNY NCS-145 BG-II and G.Cot.Hy-10 BG-II. Seed cotton yield (kg/ha) was significantly higher for AJIT -199 BG-II followed by AJIT -155 BG-II and JAY BT under unprotected condition

Biochemical and Jassid Population: Biochemical parameters were done from leaf samples at 30, 60 and 90 DAS and Jassid per three leaves data were collected at 30, 60 and 90 DAS.

Table 2 showed Jassid population and primary and secondary metabolites level of genotypes at 30 DAS. Jassid population (No/3

leaves) was significantly differed among BT genotypes under unprotected condition. Protein content was found in range of 2.25 to 8.75 mg/g of fresh leaf tissue under unprotected condition while phenol content was in range of 2.41 to 4.45 mg/g of fresh leaf. Highest phenol content was recorded in AJIT -199 BG-II and lower phenol content and higher reducing sugar was found in G.Cot.Hy-8 BG-II. Tannin content was found highest in ANKUR-3028 BG-II followed by AJIT-155BG-II while it was lowest in RHC-II BG-II. Flavanoid and Gossypol content were significantly differed among BT genotypes under unprotected condition.

Table 3 showed Jassid population and primary and secondary metabolites level of genotypes at 60 DAS. Jassid population (No/3 leaves) was significantly differed among BT genotypes under unprotected condition. Highest Jassid population was found in RHC-II Bg-II (2.80/3 leaves). Protein content was found in range of 5.72 to 8.12 mg/g of fresh leaf tissue under unprotected condition while phenol content was in range of 5.18 to 8.49 mg/g of fresh leaf. Highest phenol content was recorded in AJIT -199 BG-II and lower phenol content was recorded in RHC-II BG-II. Higher reducing sugar was found in G.Cot.Hy-8 BG-II. Tannin content was found highest in AJIT -199 BG-II followed by AJIT-155BG-II. Flavanoid and Gossypol content were significantly differed among BT genotypes under unprotected condition.

Table 4 showed Jassid population and primary and secondary metabolites level of genotypes at 90 DAS. Jassid population (no/3 leaves) was significantly differed among BT genotypes under unprotected condition. Highest Jassid population was found in RHC-II Bg-II (3.51/3 leaves). Protein content was found in range of 7.33 to 8.94 mg/g of fresh leaf tissue under unprotected condition while phenol content was in range of 5.89 to 10.49 mg/g of fresh leaf. Highest phenol content was recorded in GTHH-49 BG-II followed by AJIT -155 BG-II and lower phenol content was recorded in RHC-II BG-II. Lower reducing sugar was found in AJIT -199 BG-II. Tannin content was found highest in AJIT -155 BG-II followed by BUNNY NCS-145 BG-II. Flavanoid and Gossypol content were significantly differed among BT genotypes under unprotected condition. Higher gossypol content was found in AJIT-199 BG-II. While it was lower in AANKUR-3028 BG-II.

Biplot analysis for the metabolites estimated in relation to insect incidence data: Biplots were constructed between the insect incidence data and the individual metabolite concentration in the genotypes recorded at 30 DAS. The plots indicated that the genotype exhibiting higher concentrations of the metabolite possesses lesser insect incidence (Q2). Fig.1 indicates that ANKUR- 3028 BG-II, AJIT-155 BG-II and AJIT -199 BG-II (22.81, 22.36 and 20.66 mg/100g dry weight) of tannin content among Ankur-3028 BG-II have lowest incidence of *Jassid*. Fig.2 indicates that (4.45 mg/g of tissue) of phenol found in AJIT-155 BG-II. Fig.3 & Fig.4 indicates that in G. Cot. Hy. 12 BG-II showed highest flavanol content and gossypol content have lower incidence of *Jassid*.

Conclusion:

Seed cotton yield (kg/ha) was significantly higher for AJIT -199 BG-II followed by AJIT -155 BG-II and JAY BT under unprotected condition while AJIT-155 BG-II have lowest Jassid population at 60 and 60 DAS.

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Table 1. Growth characters and seed cotton as influenced by Genotypes

Treatments	Plant height (cm) at harvest	No. of monopodia at harvest	No. of sympodia at harvest	No. of Bolls	Boll weight (g)	Seed cotton yield (kg/ha)	Final Plant population (no. /net plot)
G.Cot.Hy-8 BG-II	96.0	0.8	21.2	31.8	3.31	1987.34	28.33
G.Cot.Hy-10 BG-II	106.7	0.0	20.2	26.7	4.00	1632.76	29.00
G.Cot.Hy-12 BG-II	122.8	0.0	23.8	32.3	3.92	2154.32	30.00
GTHH-49 BG-II	117.2	0.3	19.2	36.5	3.38	2241.78	26.33
RHC-II BG-II	96.2	1.5	18.3	28.3	3.84	1840.72	28.33
ANKUR- 3028 BG-II	116.8	0.3	21.0	28.9	3.61	1626.89	28.33
AJIT -155 BG-II	118.7	0.0	23.2	36.3	3.99	2575.85	28.00
AJIT -199 BG-II	125.0	0.0	22.0	30.5	4.62	2581.71	29.67
BUNNY NCS-145 BG-II	101.2	0.5	19.8	26.1	4.02	1683.51	29.00
JAY BT	113.5	0.3	21.7	30.8	3.90	2284.93	29.33
S. Ed	8.52	0.30	2.14	3.21	0.28	276.5	1.67
CD (5%)	18.05	0.65	N.S.	6.8	0.61	585.5	N.S.

Table 2. Jassid population (No/plant), primary and secondary metabolites level of genotypes at 30 DAS

Treatments	Jassid population (No/Plant)	Protein (mg/g of tissue)	Phenol (mg/g of tissue)	Reducing sugar (mg/g of tissue)	Tannin (mg/100g dry weight)	Flavanoid (mg/g of tissue)	Gossypol (%)
G.Cot.Hy-8 BG-II	0.33	2.25	2.41	8.86	13.56	9.75	0.39
G.Cot.Hy-10 BG-II	0.33	3.61	2.95	8.05	15.26	7.28	0.31
G.Cot.Hy-12 BG-II	0.67	2.34	3.12	7.75	19.19	5.76	0.36
GTHH-49 BG-II	1.33	6.33	4.18	8.07	13.05	4.61	0.36
RHC-II BG-II	2.67	3.73	2.90	7.25	12.15	5.15	0.26
ANKUR- 3028 BG-II	1.33	4.41	3.52	6.63	22.81	6.10	0.33
AJIT -155 BG-II	0.67	6.65	4.45	6.13	22.36	8.96	0.34
AJIT -199 BG-II	0.67	6.66	3.68	8.08	20.66	6.10	0.34
BUNNY NCS-145 BG-II	1.00	8.75	3.05	7.53	15.75	6.87	0.25
JAY BT	0.33	8.69	4.12	8.35	17.22	5.11	0.23
SEd	0.41	0.033	0.039	0.025	0.25	0.033	0.021
CD (5%)	0.88	0.068	0.082	0.045	0.54	0.070	0.044

Table 3. Jassid population (No/plant) , primary and secondary metabolites level of genotypes at 60 DAS

Treatments	Jassiid population (No/Plant)	Protein (mg/g of tissue)	Phenol (mg/g of tissue)	Reducing sugar (mg/g of tissue)	Tannin (mg/100g dry weight)	Flavanoid (mg/g of tissue)	Gossypol (%)
G.Cot.Hy-8 BG-II	1.00	5.72	5.42	16.37	28.63	8.37	0.41
G.Cot.Hy-10 BG-II	1.33	6.27	6.17	11.63	14.65	8.13	0.33
G.Cot.Hy-12 BG-II	3.67	6.20	6.38	11.15	18.12	8.07	0.26
GTHH-49 BG-II	4.00	6.66	6.85	9.18	23.87	8.58	0.26
RHC-II BG-II	4.33	6.25	5.18	10.55	28.13	7.39	0.35
ANKUR- 3028 BG-II	2.67	8.10	5.27	10.28	30.04	8.66	0.26
AJIT -155 BG-II	0.67	8.12	7.92	12.44	30.70	9.38	0.31
AJIT -199 BG-II	2.00	6.61	8.49	10.84	31.39	4.44	0.26
BUNNY NCS-145 BG-II	3.00	8.09	6.83	10.26	23.89	8.84	0.28
JAY BT	4.33	7.76	5.32	11.63	18.93	8.45	0.35
SEd	0.78	0.037	0.031	0.099	0.105	0.035	0.020
CD (5%)	1.66	0.077	0.064	0.207	0.220	0.073	0.041

Table 4. Jassid population (No/plant), primary and secondary metabolites level of genotypes at 90 DAS

Treatments	Jassiid population (No/Plant)	Protein (mg/g of tissue)	Phenol (mg/g of tissue)	Reducing sugar (mg/g of tissue)	Tannin (mg/100g dry weight)	Flavanoid (mg/g of tissue)	Gossypol (%)
G.Cot.Hy-8 BG-II	3.67	8.65	6.86	22.71	13.85	7.35	0.58
G.Cot.Hy-10 BG-II	2.33	7.96	9.75	23.08	19.71	8.14	0.56
G.Cot.Hy-12 BG-II	4.00	7.36	9.90	25.51	15.89	6.81	0.62
GTHH-49 BG-II	4.00	8.58	10.90	20.52	24.23	8.18	0.37
RHC-II BG-II	7.67	7.45	5.89	20.55	29.85	6.72	0.62
ANKUR- 3028 BG-II	2.33	7.33	7.67	17.74	30.45	7.36	0.36
AJIT -155 BG-II	2.67	8.12	10.46	21.37	46.54	8.51	0.56
AJIT -199 BG-II	5.00	8.94	9.22	16.15	39.86	7.80	0.72
BUNNY NCS-145 BG-II	4.67	7.38	8.20	21.14	46.07	6.84	0.61
JAY BT	5.00	8.38	6.86	26.37	26.24	5.93	0.66
SEd	1.38	0.022	0.047	0.029	0.28	0.027	0.019
CD (5%)	2.92	0.047	0.099	0.066	0.59	0.056	0.040

Fig. 1: Tannin (g/100g of dry tissue)

Fig.2: Phenol (mg/g of tissue)

Fig. 3: Flavanoid content (mg/g of tissue)

Fig. 4: Gossypol content (%)

